

APOPTOSIS. THE ROLE OF APOPTOSIS IN CANCERS**Orlov Alina,**

Undergraduate Student

*Nicolae Testimîțanu State University of Medicine and Pharmacy
bd. Ștefan cel Mare și Sfânt 165, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova***Dumitraș Grigore**

Doctor of medical sciences, Associate professor,

Department of Histology, Cytology and Embryology,

*State University of Medicine and Pharmacy „Nicolae Testimîțanu” Republic of Moldova, Chișinău***Abstract**

Apoptosis is a complex mechanism that is involved at any stage during organism development or in cellular damage. It is triggered by specific external and internal factors such as ultraviolet radiation, hypoxia, growth factors, viruses, and bacteria, which activate the two main pathways: the extrinsic pathway, also known as the death receptor pathway, and the intrinsic mitochondrial pathway. Research on the apoptotic pathway has proven to be a highly effective method in the search for new therapies against cancer, which is a process of uncontrolled cellular growth and division. In this paper, I will review the main molecular apoptotic mechanisms and their connection in the process of oncogenesis, as well as the most innovative preparations whose mechanisms involve apoptotic pathways and modulators.

Keywords: apoptosis, extrinsic pathway, intrinsic pathway, cancer

Introduction

The term "apoptosis" is of Greek origin and refers to the natural process by which leaves fall from trees during autumn or petals fall from blooming flowers. In 1972, Kerr, Wyllie, and Currie introduced this term to describe a distinct morphological mode of cell death.[8] It is a process regulated by cysteine proteins called caspases and the Bcl2 family of proteins. Programmed cell death plays an essential role in development and cellular homeostasis and is involved in the elimination of damaged cells. From a molecular standpoint, there are two main pathways through which apoptosis occurs: the extrinsic pathway, mediated by receptors activated by external factors, and the intrinsic pathway, mediated by mitochondria and produced by intracellular factors.[6]

The extrinsic pathway

The extrinsic pathway is triggered by stimuli from the cell's external environment, such as ultraviolet rays, hypoxia, hyperthermia, etc., and is initiated either by the binding and oligomerization of transmembrane proteins from the death receptor family or by reaching a certain extracellular concentration of specific factors. This leads to the transmission of lethal signals or dependence receptors to initiate the apoptotic process.[2]

The activation of the extrinsic apoptotic pathway occurs through interactions between ligand-receptors from the TNF family. The main receptors are FAS, DR5, TNFR1, and the most important ligands are TNF, FasL, TRAIL, and TL1A. After ligand binding to the receptor, receptor trimerization occurs, followed by the recruitment of adaptor proteins: TRADD and FADD. In the next step, the adaptor proteins recruit pro-

caspase-8 and form the signaling complex that induces death-DISC. Consequently, DISC activates caspase-8. The activation of caspase-8 leads to the initiation of apoptosis through two mechanisms. The first mechanism involves the activation of caspase-3, while the second mechanism involves the cleavage of the BH3-interacting domain death agonist (BID), a pro-apoptotic protein from the Bcl-2 family. The cleaved BID becomes tBID and translocates to mitochondria [5,9].

The intrinsic pathway

This pathway is also known as the mitochondrial pathway and can be activated by a wide variety of external stimuli such as radiation, osmotic stress, metabolic stress, lack of growth factors, loss of adhesion, and DNA damage. Upon activation of this pathway, cytochrome c is released from the intermembrane space of mitochondria into the cytosol [10,7]. Intracellular stress activates BH3 proteins and inhibits anti-apoptotic proteins in the Bcl2 class, leading to oligomerization and activation of pro-apoptotic proteins BAX and BAK, forming pores in the outer mitochondrial membrane, causing its permeabilization (MOMP), which leads to the release of cytochrome c and the second mitochondrial activator of caspases (SMAC). Cytochrome c binds to apoptotic protease-activating factor 1 (APAF1) and procaspase-9 to form the apoptosome, where procaspase-9 dimerizes and becomes activated, then triggering a cascade of caspases. The activated caspase-9 heterodimer cleaves and activates the effector caspases -3 and -7. At the same time, SMAC inhibits X-linked inhibitor of apoptosis (XIAP), facilitating the activation of procaspase-3 and -7. [7]

Figure 1. The intrinsic apoptotic pathway [7]

The role of programmed cell death in cancer

Apoptosis plays a crucial role in controlling tumor formation and influences how tumor cells respond to currently available treatments. However, most cancer cells are capable of resisting apoptosis through internal mechanisms and find other strategies to avoid cell death. [4] Studies indicate that tumor cells are more sensitive to the extrinsic pathway of apoptosis than the intrinsic pathway, suggesting that cancer therapy should focus on this pathway. Other factors involved in apoptosis, such as oncogenes and tumor suppressors, can influence the process and contribute to the avoidance of apoptosis by cancer cells. [1]

New therapies target proteins involved in regulating apoptosis, such as the BCL-2 family of proteins, and can promote cell death in cancer cells. One innovative drug is Navitoclax, which inhibits the Bcl-2, BclXL, and Bcl-w proteins that are essential for the Bcl-mediated signaling pathway. This inhibitor mimics the interaction between the BH3 domain of Bad proteins and the Bcl-2 family of proteins, triggering the apoptotic process by promoting the activity of Bax and Bak proteins. [3] A new direction of treatment is caspase-dependent gene therapy, it was reported that caspase-3 gene therapy induced cancer cell apoptosis, another tested therapy was p53-based gene therapy, it was shown that when introducing the p53 gene into cancer therapy prostate tumor cells become sensitive to radiotherapy.[8]

Conclusions

Programmed cell death has 2 main pathways: the intrinsic pathway and the extrinsic pathway. Knowledge of these apoptotic mechanisms have revolutionized cancer therapy. Caspases, the Bcl-2 protein family, the p53 protein as well as other mediators are

the basis of the mechanisms of action of some anti-cancer preparations.

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